

The Non-Negligible Contribution of Rural Areas to Europe’s Innovation Ambitions

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Our AEIDL Expert on Rural and Territorial Development, Carla Lostrangio, *provides evidence of the contribution of community-led rural innovation to both Europe’s competitiveness and territorial cohesion, and provides recommendations to strengthen it in the next EU budget based on the emerging findings¹ from our FUTURAL Project.*

Europe’s Innovation Challenge

The 2025 Competitiveness Compass, the EU Startup and Scale Up Strategy, the EU Innovation Act, and ultimately the [post-2027 Multi-Annual Financial Framework](#) (MFF) share the same mission: taking the EU back to the position of a global innovation leader. However, these **policy documents fail to fully embed and benefit from rural areas’ contribution to innovation**. The increased centralisation of the EU’s budget via the so-called National and Regional Partnership Plans (NRPPs), European Competitiveness Fund (ECF) and the elimination of minimum earmarking for community-led local development are undesirable signs of this failure.

Drawing from our [FUTURAL Project](#) where AEIDL has produced an assessment of [Existing Policy and Governance frameworks](#), this brief provides an analysis of the **state of the art** of policies for community-led rural innovation (aka, what works and what does not). Findings are framed to inform the [post-2027 MFF proposal of the Commission](#), presented in July 2025, and ensure that the **EU’s budget is able to unlock the potential of community-led innovation** in pursuing the [EU Strategic Priorities](#) of innovation and competitiveness.

(Under)Valued Community-led innovation

Since 1991, community-led development has grown successfully across the EU thanks to the LEADER programme, expanding rapidly from 217 Local Action Groups in 1991 to 2,678 (2023-27)². Community-led development puts local communities at the **heart of transformative change**, allowing them to take **ownership** of the strategic development of their own territories and to craft **place-based and meaningful solutions** to complex territorial challenges. Community-led innovation denotes types of innovation which are designed and driven by **local actors**, ranging across technological, social, organisational or economic solutions. Additionally, community-led innovations span across **several sectors** (Table 1). In rural areas, community-led innovation is essential to address gaps in the provision of goods and services, which remain unanswered by public institutions or the private market. In doing so, they allow rural citizens to exercise the so-called new [EU right to stay](#) and live in rural areas.

Table 1. Community-led Innovation: Types and Potential

Type/Sector	Challenges Addressed	Figures
Energy communities	Energy Poverty, Resource Autonomy.	9,000 energy communities (2024); 1.5 mln citizens involved ³
Agri-food communities (e.g. community-supported agriculture, community gardens, soil regenerative practices)	Short food supply chain, food accessibility, food security, fair remuneration to farmers, environmental degradation food quality	6,300 CSA initiatives for approx. 0.5 mln eaters ⁴
Nature-friendly and circular communities	Sustainable management of resources (e.g. water, soil, waste); Nature Restoration, Circular economy practices	Only in Belgium: 203 Repair Cafes, 35,000 repaired objects, 2,000 tonnes CO2 prevented, 218 tonnes waste prevented ⁵
Climate communities (e.g. transition towns, ecovillages)	Climate and biodiversity collapse	Approx. 1,000 eco-villages, eco-projects, networks ⁶
Social and solidarity economy (e.g. social enterprises)	Social cohesion, ageing and inclusivity, local development, access to basic services	N/A ⁷
Community-based healthcare collective ⁸	Healthcare, access to basic services	The international network currently counts collectives in 4 countries
Community-based mobility (e.g. carsharing)	Transport poverty, remoteness	N/A

The Policy and Governance Thread

In our recent [report](#), we reviewed the contribution of **>40 EU-level policies, strategies and initiatives** relevant to community-led innovation, with a specific emphasis to rural areas. Our analysis investigated policies targeting rural and regional development as well as sectoral policies (e.g. innovation, industry, care, education & skills, digital). In addition, we mapped **>50 EU-level governance mechanisms** which function to strengthen community-led innovations

There is a delicate link between policy and governance frameworks for community-led innovation. Policies ensure support for community-led initiatives is not left up to the shifting national priorities, whereas governance mechanisms are essential to design, monitor and implement policies.

Insights from the Policy and Governance Findings

State of Art on Policies

At present, a broad number of EU-level policies, strategies and initiatives can be used to support **community-led innovation**, in theory⁹. In practice, the CAP's LEADER programme (2023-2027) is **the only programme having a legislative earmarking for community-led development in rural areas** (innovation is one of the seven essential ingredients). The Cohesion Policy provides a minimum earmark only for **community-led initiatives in urban areas**, though supporting measures for rural areas are strongly encouraged. Additionally, the EU calls Member States (MSs) to support community-led initiatives via Smart Villages, Startup Villages and other programmes. The box below reports our key findings on how EU policy's support (and gaps) with respect to CLI in rural areas over the current policy period (2021-2027).

Cohesion Policy's Role: Allocates more funds to rural development beyond farming than CAP Pillar II, but LEADER (under CAP) is by far more relevant for financing community-led initiatives. Lack of CLLD earmarking in Cohesion Policy could explain a low uptake of community-led approach in MSs Operational Programmes.

LEADER's popularity and limitations: Highly valued by local communities, it however faces structural, bureaucratic limitations and incomplete territorial coverage. Recent criticisms from the EU Court of Auditors (2022) should be truthfully addressed.

Smart Villages: Represent an untapped potential for community-led innovation within CAP and Cohesion Policy. Overall, MSs were reluctant to set up ambitious targets and allocate budgets. Only 5 MSs designed fully dedicated Smart Villages interventions and 18 MSs embedded them in existing LEADER interventions (2023-27)¹⁰. There are no figures of Smart Villages' uptake in Cohesion Policy.

Beyond CAP/Cohesion: Sectoral programs (e.g., Horizon Europe, New EU Bauhaus, Social Climate Funds) offer alternatives to diversity fund for rural innovation but are often spatially blind or less accessible to local initiatives (excessive bureaucracy or competition, funds are too large to be managed by communities).

Lack of Ad-hoc strategies and policy misalignment: Most analysed countries lack specific policies for community-led innovation, and these are often poorly integrated by sectoral policies on digital and social innovation. Limited policy misaligned with innovation and industrial policies/strategies is a critical issue at national and EU level (e.g. EU Competitiveness Compass).

Table 2 compares the main policy instruments supporting community-led rural innovation over the current and the future programming period. As shown below, the European Commission (EC) proposal for the MFF, tabled in July 2025, is likely to **erode support to community-led rural innovation**.

Table 2. Comparison of key measures for community-led innovation between current and post-2027 EU Budget

Policies, programme, initiative	CLI-support (2021-27)	CLI-support (2028-2034) ¹¹
LEADER	Foreseen under CAP Pillar II, with a 5% min. earmarking , to be designed by EU MSs	Maintained under CAP Draft Regulation but no min. earmarking
AKIS/EIP- AGRI	Mandatory, funded via in the CAP Pillar II	Maintained under CAP Draft Regulation but no budget line
CLLD	Under the Cohesion Policy with an 8% min. earmarking for urban areas. Designed with EU MSs	Encouraged support under the National Regional Partnership Plans but no min. earmarking
Smart Villages	Encouraged by the EU but not mandatory. KPIs defined by EU MSs	Smart Villages mentioned but only marginally
New European Bauhaus	Yes, both rural and urban	Mentioned but unclear
FP10- Horizon Europe	Living Labs. Both rural and urban according to the call description	Support continued but tight to the ECF priorities and more focus on higher technology readiness levels

What innovation type receives more policy support today?

At present, **digital innovation** is the mostly targeted form of innovation by mapped policies. This is not a surprise given the EU priorities on the digital transition. To a slightly lesser extent, policy supports community-led development and social innovation.

Rural areas remain in the scope of the majority of the mapped policy frameworks with a few exceptions (e.g. Next Generation EU, EU New Industrial Strategy, EU Skills Agenda). These exceptions should not be overlooked. Contrariwise, they demonstrate that it is possible to pledge for supporting innovative actions in rural areas through other sectoral programmes (e.g. within digital and economic policies or industrial policies).

Nearly 75% of mapped policies target – by means of their objectives and/or specific measures - at the same time rural development and innovation (between social innovation, digital innovation, community-led) **and 40% of mapped policies target rural development and all forms of innovation**. This is particularly important as rural areas are often called to solve multi-sectoral and complex challenges for which a **policy mix** would be particularly beneficial.

What support do community-led initiatives receive today?

Technical and capacity building is the first type of support provided by the policy frameworks mapped in our study (70%), followed by **economic and financial support** (58%). An example of capacity building support is assistance and funding to prepare LEADER and Smart Villages Strategies. Economic and financial support is provided both through shared management funds (e.g. LEADER, CLLD) and direct management funds (e.g. Horizon Europe, LIFE).

Nearly 50% of the mapped policy frameworks foresee **political and legal support**, meaning that community-led innovation is enshrined into legislative documents/basis and therefore have a legal relevance and/or binding implications. The mandatory **minimum allocation** to the LEADER programme into the current CAP policy (5% of EAFRD funds) is an example of how legislative support can act as a **guarantee** for Member State commitment to local innovation¹².

More than half of these policy strategies, initiatives and legislations support the **sharing of information, data and existing practices**. Knowledge is perceived as one of the critical points to build the capacities of communities and inspire their action. **Approximately 50% of mapped frameworks are aimed at supporting the EU legislative process through advocacy or stakeholder engagement**. To a lesser (yet still important) extent, these frameworks are used for consulting stakeholders, encouraging networking and peer-to-peer learning, and piloting innovative solutions and practices.

State of the Art on Governance and whose voices are heard in the discussion

Our study mapped relevant governance mechanisms – working groups, thematic experts, networks etc – supporting community-led rural innovation. At EU level, 29% of mapped mechanisms have a **mixed composition**, meaning that they gather different target groups. To a lesser extent, there are groups involving only the main type of actors, such as national authorities (16%), EU institutional actors and multi-level public authorities (13% each). The least represented are groups involving only or predominantly local authorities, research & academia, civil society & NGOs, or other actors.

Figure 1 Most predominant actor groups involved in the identified governance frameworks. Source: Own Elaboration.

Approximately 85% of mapped governance frameworks focus on **policy advocacy and advice** for rural development. This means that this list is a very good starting point for organisations that wish to get more engaged on EU policy making related to rural matters. While this is not definitive, it provides a potential quick start tool to familiarise with relevant bodies and structures acting at different moments of the policy cycle.

Among key governance mechanisms, the **Rural Pact** is the EU-level framework for cooperation on rural development. It connects rural actors, reinforces their voices and promotes coordinated action across the EU. In only 2 years, the EU Rural Pact developed a **joint Declaration**, promoted **cross-learning** and reinforced **national and regional** implementation of the Pact.

EU Governance mechanisms: EU Funding Treaties and existing governance mechanisms offer (in theory) legislative and operational basis for advocate for stronger support for community-led rural innovation, but (in practice) they are too complex for communities to understand and engage with. The re-nationalisation and weak integration of the **Partnership Principle** in next MFF's draft proposal exacerbates this even further.

Constrained national space for communities: country- support to communities varies across MSs according to the level of state centralization, historical governance, and local financial autonomy. Local authorities and civil society networks are the closest tier to communities but are increasingly financially constrained, facing imbalance between local duties and municipal size (e.g., 'right on municipal uniformity' in Spain), geopolitical instability.

Technical and Financial Needs: Lack of these resources is a major barrier. Excessive bureaucracy or rigid regulations harshen this.

The Budget Thunderstorm

The 2021-2027 budget

The EC calculates that **8% of the current 2023-2027 CAP allocations** against **16% of the 2021-2027 Cohesion Policy**¹³ budget goes to rural areas beyond farming¹⁴. When it comes to **funding reaching community-led innovation in rural areas**, the current CAP legal framework provides that **at least 5% of the EU MSs financial envelopes** shall be earmarked to support community-led innovation in rural areas via the LEADER programme (i.e. approx. € 4.77 billion).

In the 2021-27 Cohesion Policy, **12 EU MSs** planned investments of **€1.6 billion under community led local development strategies**, mainly in rural areas and nearly **€ 750 million** have been planned to support **bottom-up community-led local development strategies via the ERDF and ESF+**, with an almost equal split between urban and rural areas¹⁵. It has also been estimated that at least **10.2% of Recovery and Resilience Facility** expenditure (approx. €50 billion), has been primarily targeted to Territorial Cohesion¹⁶.

However, as emerged from the Rural Pact policy lab¹⁷, the **monitoring of funding reaching rural areas** is still insufficiently granular and inconsistent across EU MSs. The EC does not have clear cut data on how much of the EU budget reaches rural areas, especially beyond the CAP Pillar II on rural development, and mostly rely on estimates.

The 2028-2034 Budget Proposal

A tempest has arisen from the EC proposal for the 2028-2034 MFF well before its publication. By calling for greater **simplification**, this proposal introduces significant changes in terms of the EU's budget structure. At the heart of this proposal, the EC plans to **consolidate nearly all EU funding streams into a single, coherent strategy** per Member State (going to 540 programming documents to 27 National Regional Partnership Plans and one Interreg Plan). These programmes would deal with policy sectors linked to agriculture and cohesion. Additionally, a new mega fund (aka the **EU Competitiveness Fund**) would be instituted to drive competitiveness and innovation in strategic sectors (Figure 2).

The current CAP Pillar II would be integrated into the cohesion chapter of the NRPP, having hence to compete with broader cohesion priorities. Thus far, the EC proposal encourages community-led innovation, but it **removes any minimum allocation to LEADER and CLLD**, and it does not set any target or indicators for **Smart Villages**. On the other hand, the proposal MFF places a strong emphasis on **reducing administrative burden for beneficiaries** enhancing Simplified Cost Options, including mandatory lump sums for projects up to EUR 20,000.

Figure 2 EC proposal for post-27 budget. Source: European Commission. An ambitious budget for a stronger Europe. 16/07/25.

Policy Options for the next MFF

FUTURAL first set of policy ideas		How to integrate them in the post-2027 MFF proposal
1	Formally recognise the transformative role of community-led innovation	Integrate community-led innovation in the ECF Regulation
2	Mainstream Political & Financial Support with 8% Mandatory Earmarking and Territorially Proof all EU Policies	Require mandatory earmarking for the NRPPs
3	Apply the 'Do not harm to EU Cohesion' principle across all territorially relevant EU policies	Reinstate the principle in the new MFF
4	Align Rural Development with Sectoral Policies reinforcing existing Governance mechanisms	Ensure territorially targets are defined under all chapters of the NRPPs
5	Shift the Focus to Rural Innovation Ecosystems rather than individual solutions	Define a territorial target for rural innovation in the ECF and FP10; define min. participation of rural stakeholder to ECF & FP10 advisory bodies; Ensure funding for small-scale projects and projects pursuing all Technological and Social Readiness Levels
6	Allow Regulatory Flexibility to allow innovation to happen now	Simplify rules for innovation procurement
7	Enhance Digital Skills & infrastructures , with caution on marginalised communities	Address the rural-urban gap via the ESF+ and ECF
8	Systematise Inclusion of Local Voices beyond Tokenistic Approaches	Require MS to define clear measures to implement the EU Partnership Principle at all stages of NRPP (design, implementation, evaluation); Reinstate commitment to the continuation of the EU Rural Pact.

Disclaimer

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Endnotes

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- 2 5 bn EUR (7.7% of EAFRD), covering approximately 65% of the rural population in the EU-27.
- 3 <https://interreg-danube.eu/projects/nrgcom/news/recent-survey-highlights-potential-of-energy-communities-in-the-eu#:~:text=As%20of%20early%202024%2C%20there,consume%20their%20own%20renewable%20energy>
- 4 URGENCI (2016). *Overview of community supported Agriculture in Europe*. ISBN: 976-2-9551195-5-6
- 5 [Repair Cafés in figures - Repair Together](#)
- 6 GEN Europe map: <https://gen-europe.org/discover/ecovillage-map/>
- 7 SERIGO (2025) *Mapping and assessing SI and SSE solutions in Europe*.
- 8 <https://inosc.net/about-inosc/who-we-are/>
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- 11 https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/eu-budget/long-term-eu-budget/eu-budget-2028-2034_en
- 12 [Microsoft Word - Updated ELARD position on the future of LEADER CLLD approved_GA_20190410](#)
- 13 This percentage raises to 24% when included funds directly and explicitly allocated also to mountain areas and islands (EC, 2024)
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